

BENEFITS OF ISO/IEC 17025 ACCREDITATION

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Abstract. *ISO/IES 17025 sets general requirements for the competence of laboratories and organizations performing testing and calibration. This standard plays an important role in ensuring the accuracy and reliability of results obtained in laboratories by establishing a quality management system, personnel requirements, measurement methods and traceability of measurements. Compliance with ISO/IES 17025 helps demonstrate the laboratory's competence and increases confidence in its results. This standard is of great importance to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the results obtained in laboratories. It promotes the establishment of high standards of competence and independence, which in turn guarantees the quality of laboratory work. This approach is necessary to ensure confidence in the obtained analytical and test results.*

Keywords: *ISO/IEC 17025 standard, accreditation, laboratory, calibration, technical assessment.*

Introduction. This standard establishes general requirements for the competence, impartiality and sound functioning of laboratories. This standard is applicable to all organizations involved in laboratory activities, regardless of the number of personnel. Laboratory clients, regulatory bodies, peer assessment organizations and schemes, accreditation bodies, and other parties apply this standard when confirming or recognizing the competence of laboratories.

ISO (eng-“international”) Organization for Standardization, ISO - standards work issuer International organization existence Considered about standardization International organization in 1946 ISA (International Federation of the National Standardization Association, 1926, New York) and UNSCC (United Nations Standards Coordination Committee, 1944) organizations based on 25 standardizations national organizations to organize made.

ISO/IEC 17025 (see General). requirements for that competence from testing oath calibration laboratory", "Testing and calibration laboratory ability to be placed requirements") test and calibration laboratory quality management standard existence is considered.

Standard English language version originally in 1999 adoption made _ Test and calibration laboratory have technical approvals and technically _ justified results to obtain capable of what to show. If you want, by default it is for execution that one row of requirements is determined. This is a standard application of a laboratory and another organization with a mutually collaborating institution, in particular, research Results and calibration of the work of another country to accept being taken will come.

The ISO/IEC 17025 standard metrological organizations itself has a special function account obtained without ISO 9001 quality management to the model is based on In particular, the ISO/IEC 17025 standard is included in the ISO 9001 standard. national accreditation bodies to the laboratory from accreditation transfer and technical competence of the laboratory how accessible the concept did not work.

The laboratory must be responsible, through legally binding obligations, for the management of all information received externally or acquired in the course of carrying out

laboratory activities. The laboratory must inform the customer in advance about the information that it intends to make publicly available. An exception is information that becomes publicly available by decision of the customer or by agreement between the laboratory and the customer (for example, for the purpose of responding to complaints). All other information is considered to be a trade secret and must be treated as confidential. Laboratory requirements ISO/IEC 17025 compliance with ISO 9001 standard means too. Accreditation (lat. accredo- "to believe") an object (center or province) of activity standard a certain indicator, criterion and requirements suitable to come officially confirmation of the process of existence is considered.

ISO/IEC 17025 standard in the laboratory research power within the limits of what is being done and reliable results the gift that it does show give the opportunity gives, with this together too national too the world scale trust level increase the reason will be. Examine reports and certificates of another country, addition without checks, acceptance will be done, while your own in turn International trade and qualification exchange development take will come.

Who is ISO/IEC 17025 intended for? intended? From the ISO/IEC 17025 test transfer, an example of receiving or calibration with is engaged and reliable The results of receiving are wanted by everyone as in the organization to apply for intended.

Standard state, production of the issuer of the company or other organization applicable was everyone, like in laboratories, the application can

In addition, this Standard University, scientific research centers, verified transfer, samples to receive or calibration required was governments, inspection bodies, products certification organizations and other compatibility to determine in the authorities too the application can

In the laboratory, the quality is managed system as an application you need to do you need Accreditation of customer laboratories is carried out research quality and power was the confidence to provide a mechanism for existence It is believed.

The client's accreditation laboratory to test, measure or research transfer to the field require satisfaction, as well as research and measurement of some types in transfer its technical capabilities to officially recognize the taken existence is considered the Laboratory standard ISO/IEC 17025 requirements its compatibility from accreditation to pass the opportunity gives.

By default, two from the side consists of: laboratory management with depends on was the part and test or measure technical requirements for methods technical part, including. to the ISO/IEC 17025 standard the corresponding management system is current in achieving we are one time The requirement of the ISO 9001 standard is too because we will do it in the laboratory Quality management system with depends on was issues known part of the Quality Management System requirements depend. Laboratories from accreditation of technical competence in the transfer of assessment for a particular work developed criteria and from the procedures used.

Technical assessment in accordance with specialists in laboratories test and calibration on time information collect effect doer all comprehensive factor analysis will spend.

These criteria comply with the international standards ISO/IEC 17025 according to the standard (the whole world through laboratory assessment for is used), as well as the program for so that the computer and specification bodies work together, developed by other technical requirements based on the Laboratory from the accreditation conductor of the organization from the ISO/IEC standard 17025 laboratory test and calibration on time of course information gift achieve ability effect doer factors assessment for used. These include the following: - technical qualifications of employees; - test methods reliability and goal compatibility; - measurement and

calibrations are compatible with national standards; equipment test reliability, calibration and maintenance _display; test and calibration on time data quality provide; test and examine for samples, choose from them, use and transport for the conditions create

Above, as already noted, the requirements of the ISO/IEC 17025 standard for laboratories in accordance with the accreditation transfer of the ISO 9001 standard in the requirements of an approved quality management system include the same principles. From accreditation past the standard requirements of laboratories in accordance with the activity that he goes to study their activities again to check through is assessed.

Such laboratories have their powers at home, respectively, manifestation to do for regularly accordingly knowledge and skills verification, that is, a professional test or interlaboratory mutual verification in participation programs reached go need Accreditation to clients how is this useful?

The client is guaranteed reliable quality services in the system to have a technically competent laboratory he is confident in his choice; Expensive again to prevent research (for example, examination) to obtain an independent, competent third to tests or calibration laboratory to thoroughness with assessed in the client to examine was confidence increases; Costs are rejected and abroad the organization of research (for example, expert opinions) demand increases International contracts system (for example, the International Laboratories from the Accreditation Transfer Association (ILAC) mutually recognize receive about consent) for the reason, accredited laboratory information International on a scale of foreign countries to without words admit taken.

Such recognition to be taken again research (for example, repeated examinations to reduce due to costs volume or in importing countries they had the need to reduce Ready-made instruments gift reach through clients their needs to meet the provision of reliable test and calibration services find for a laboratory from accreditation transfer them to the International scale official admit to be taken provides.

Accreditation according to the ISO/IEC 17025 standard is documentary evidence that the company adheres to high quality standards and responsibly approaches the solution of its goals and objectives. One of the most important stages in the process of obtaining accreditation is the implementation of ISO/IEC 17025. Our company's experts will help you implement a IS according to the ISO/IEC 17025 standard and obtain accreditation. Regulatory requirements of the European Union in accordance with be From the European Union an assistant in obtaining resources (subsidies, loans). the opportunity increases. International, regional or national standards, or other recognized technical requirements containing sufficient and accurate information about. how to conduct laboratory activities do not need to be supplemented or rewritten as internal laboratory procedures if the standards are written in such a way that they can be applied by laboratory production personnel. For variable method steps or for additional detailed description, additional documentation may be required.

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